

Balancing Vocational and Academic Approaches in Maritime Education and Training: A Case Study

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Abstract: The training of seafarers has traditionally been vocational, emphasizing the acquisition of practical skills for specific tasks. On the other hand, the academic approach prioritizes critical thinking and inquiry skills over hands-on training. In recent years, however, maritime education has evolved towards a blend of both approaches, combining vocational training with academic coursework. This shift presents both advantages and challenges. This study investigates the implications of delivering a program that meets the standard training, certification, and watchkeeping (STCW) convention requirements while incorporating academic courses leading to academic degrees in nautical science and marine engineering. It also explores the impact of integrating academic requirements on the quality of graduates. The study also highlights the opportunities and critical challenges facing current and future maritime education. Quantitative and qualitative research methodologies were employed to gather data for this study, utilizing online questionnaires and interviews. It was found that the advantages and motivations in integrating the two approaches include adequately preparing graduates for industry demands, providing diverse career opportunities, making graduates attractive to a broader range of employers, and meeting the demands of accrediting and licensing bodies. These findings have practical implications for the maritime industry, as they can guide the development of future training programs. However, finding qualified instructors, retaining experienced faculty members, and dealing with financial challenges in maintaining the programs were identified as key challenges for delivering such programs. The outcome also outlines policy directions to prepare the domestic workforce for the future in the maritime industry. The paper closes with some conclusions and recommendations related to future research.

Keywords: *Maritime Education, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Advanced Technology, Environmental Sustainability*

I. INTRODUCTION

The operation of ships safely and efficiently depends primarily on a skilled and competent workforce (Lewin 2015; Mazhari 2018). The literature consistently identified human error as one of the leading contributing causes of 80% of maritime casualties (Fenucci, 1990; IMO, 2005; Emad, 2011). Maritime education, training, and certification are vital components of maritime safety, and they are considered

critical to decreasing the number of accidents in the maritime sector.

Traditionally, on-the-job (OJB) training was the norm for seafarers to learn their trade where their performance depended heavily on experience Kennerly (2002). They started as young apprentices and were mentored by their senior seamen. Through practice and instructions, they received on the job, they became competent seafarers (Kennerly 2002; Emad 2011).

Kennerly (2002) indicated that training had become more formalized, and many seafarers started their apprenticeships and learning journeys at training establishments on shore. These establishments were generally operated by governments or sometimes by the industry or individual shipping companies. He also indicated that new issues and concerns about seafarers' traditional education and training had emerged. As the shipping industry became more and more international, there were some concerns related to the need for more skills and competency of the merchant officers Kennerly (2002). This change and technological advancements in the shipping industry in the past few decades have significantly affected seafarers' maritime education and training. Thus, there is a need for international governance and standardization of regulations in the industry. To address the industry's needs, the International Maritime Organization (IMO), and International Labour Organization (ILO) played essential roles in developing and implementing international regulations.

The first attempts at codifying international training of seafarers were undertaken under the auspices of the ILO (C53) of 1936. Article 3 states that "no person shall be engaged to perform or shall perform on board any vessel to which this Convention applies the duties of master or skipper, navigating officer in charge of a watch, chief engineer, or engineer officer in charge of a watch, unless he holds a certificate of competency to perform such duties, issued or approved by the public authority of the territory where the vessel is registered."

Lewin (2015) reported that formal requirements were introduced in the twentieth century due to major maritime accidents, technological advancements, and compulsory schooling. This was the beginning of the transition from on-the-job training to the classroom.

The STCW International Convention was the first international convention to set technical standards for seafarers (IMO 1997). It entered into force in 1984 (Mazhari, 2018). However, the Convention did not achieve its purpose (Lewarn 2002; 2006; Emad 2011; Ghosh et al. 2014; Manuel 2017). Learn (2002) reported that STCW 78 focused on what seafarers needed to know to be considered competent.

Courses tended to be academic, classroom-based, teacher-centered, and assessed through formal written exams. He argued that knowing and doing something are two different things: understanding the ship-handling theory does not necessarily mean one can handle a ship. More than testing for knowledge is required.

It must be complemented by a test for doing (competence). However, he stated that the test for doing (competence), by default, includes the knowledge test. On the other hand, Manuel (2017) reported that STCW 78 needed more precision in its standards and bias towards a cognitive education paradigm whose outcomes required a more precise and correct tackle to the on-the-job competence requirements of the industry. The Convention had recommended minimum periods of seagoing and specified knowledge requirements without defining the 'skills and 'competence' required (Emad 2011).

In response to criticism of its shortcomings, the IMO revised the STCW 78 Convention in 1994. The revision rectified the perceived deficiency of skill-based competence requirements, clarified the skills and competence required, and made vital stakeholders of the Convention accountable to each other. Amendments to the STCW Convention entered into force in 1997.

The 2010 Manila Amendments to the Code, which entered into force in 2012, retains a vocational educational approach heavily influenced by competence-based training and requires specific performance-based outcomes and outcome-based assessment. The Convention specifies expected standards of competence, the associated knowledge, understanding, and proficiency required. It also defines the methods for demonstrating competence and the criteria for assessing such a demonstration of competence. Some of the changes include new requirements relating to training in modern technology, such as electronic charts and information systems, and new requirements for marine environment awareness training, as well as training in leadership and teamwork. The Amendment also introduced modern training methodology, including distance learning and web-based learning (IMO, n.d.).

The shipping industry is becoming increasingly technical and demanding a more skilled and specialized workforce ready to embrace technology's evolving changes. The current STCW, which regulates maritime education, is mainly based on existing requirements rather than the future. As a result, IMO should constantly revise the STCW considering the new policy. The mission of maritime education and training is to prepare students for today's and future requirements (Manual, 2017).

Manuel (2017) argued that the global trend in maritime education and training is increasingly shifting from vocational education that provides specific and restricted competence outcomes to more general academic components, leading to an award of academic degrees. However, as discussed earlier, seafarer education and training focus more on acquiring hands-on practical skills for performing specific tasks.

By contrast, academic education emphasizes developing in-depth analytical and critical thinking skills; cognitive skills are less dependent on hands-on, task-oriented training. The paradigm underlying academic education is the development of a mindset of inquiry where learners are challenged to question the status quo and

develop critical skills while meeting the demands of specific competencies related to specific professional standards (Manuel, 2017).

This inquiry-based approach not only focuses on acquiring specific vocational skills but also includes the development of a high level of analytical thinking and research skills. Combining the two approaches gives more opportunities for seafarers to move to other parts of the maritime business and allows the sector to have more adaptable and flexible professionals in place for future changes in ship operations (Manuel 2017; Demirel 2020).

II. MARITIME EDUCATION AND TRAINING IN OMAN

With more than 1700 km of coastline, Oman's population has maintained a profound and longstanding connection with the sea for thousands of years. Positioned between the Arabian Gulf and the western Indian Ocean, Omani mariners played pivotal roles in developing long-distance maritime trade since the Bronze Age, persisting in sailing the monsoonal trade routes until the twentieth century (Staples, 2020). Given this extensive maritime heritage, it is no surprise that Oman today is keenly interested in maritime education and training. The maritime education and training in Oman are regulated by the following entities (Figure 1):

The Directorate General of Maritime Affairs, which falls under the Ministry of Transport, Communications, and Information Technology (MTCIT), regulates and oversees all maritime training that requires issuing a Certificate of competency, Certificate of proficiency, or maritime pilotage license. The Director also oversees the implementation of IMO requirements.

The Ministry of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation (MoHERI) is responsible for licensing the establishment of HEIs and developing higher education policies.

Oman Authority for Academic Accreditation and Quality Assurance is responsible for the accreditation of HEIs and the programs they offer. The introduction of the accreditation system in Oman has greatly influenced maritime education to take a more academic approach.

Figure 1: Maritime education and training in Oman.

Maritime education and training are moving from a purely vocational approach to a combination of vocational and

academic approaches. The integration of both methods was significantly shaped by implementing Oman's quality assurance and accreditation system over the past decade, overseen by the Oman Authority for Academic Accreditation and Quality Assurance of Education (OAAQA).

On one hand, this move opened many possibilities for graduates to work onshore. On the other, it brought many challenges as the approaches differ significantly in curricula development, content, delivery, and assessment approaches. Other challenges include ensuring that faculty qualifications and the curriculum not only align with the requirements of the STCW Convention but also meet the academic standards set by the Oman Authority for Academic Accreditation and Quality Assurance (OAAQA) and the MoHERI, along with the regulations of MTCIT.

The National University of Science and Technology, IMCO of Oman, the only college offering maritime education and training in the country, was selected for this study. The objectives of this study include:

1. Identify the challenges faced in delivering maritime programs that comply with the requirements of the STCW convention while also incorporating academic courses that lead to the award of an academic degree in nautical science and marine engineering.
2. Investigate the impact of incorporating academic requirements for nautical science and marine engineering on the quality of the graduates.
3. Assess the role and level of industry stakeholders' integration in Oman's maritime education system.

III. METHODOLOGY

A comprehensive data collection strategy is necessary to effectively evaluate the methods of balancing vocational and academic approaches in Maritime Education and Training (MET). This research will employ a mixed-methods approach, utilizing quantitative and qualitative data. Quantitative data will be collected through surveys distributed to maritime professionals, educators, and students. These surveys will gauge perceptions of current curricula's effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. Qualitative data will be gathered through semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders from the maritime industry and MET institutions. This approach allows for in-depth exploration of the challenges and opportunities associated with balancing vocational and academic approaches, providing a richer understanding of the complexities involved.

A. Data Collection

Quantitative and qualitative research methodologies were employed to gather data for this study, utilizing online surveys and interviews. The semi-structured interviews were conducted with faculty members to gain a deeper understanding of the implications of incorporating academic requirements for nautical science and marine engineering, addressing topics such as the advantages and motivations in integrating academic and vocational approaches, challenges, industry stakeholder involvement, as well as their perceptions and priorities in advancing Maritime

Education and Training (MET).

B. Sampling Method

For the interviews, the purposive sampling method, a type of non-probability sampling, was employed to carefully select participants with extensive experience in either onboard vessel operations or teaching maritime courses. This technique is crucial for ensuring the quality of the data gathered, thus requiring competence and reliability among participants.

The selection criteria were based on the number of relevant years of experience, roles in the organization, and knowledge background related to the maritime industry and education field. Seven participants with excellent track records in their respective fields were selected for the study, and their details are provided in Table 1.

All interviews were conducted face-to-face to ensure insightful responses. The data analysis involved a thematic approach, through which key themes were identified and interpreted to draw conclusions and insights aligned with the study's aims and objectives.

Table 1. Interviewee details.

Participants	Position	Years of experience in the maritime industry
Participant 1	Head of Maritime Department	10
Participant 2	Assistant Professor, Marine Engineering	8
Participant 3	Lecturer, Nautical Science	16
Participant 4	Lecturer, Nautical Science	30
Participant 5	Lecturer, Marine Engineering	3
Participant 6	Lecturer, Marine Engineering	8
Participant 7	Lecturer, Marine Engineering	8

For the online survey, ten faculty members teaching marine engineering and deck officer courses, each with a minimum of 3 years of professional experience in the maritime industry, were selected. The survey was administered using Microsoft Forms. No personally identifiable data was collected. The survey link was distributed via email to the selected participants. The response rate for the online survey was 100%. The survey data were analyzed using the frequency method.

IV. FINDINGS

A. Advantages and Motivations in Integrating Academic and Vocational Approaches

The survey results indicate a consensus among participants regarding the perceived motivation and benefits of maritime programs that integrate academic courses and vocational training. Most respondents strongly agreed or agreed that such programs adequately prepare graduates for industry demands (92.9%), provide diverse career opportunities (84.9), and make graduates attractive to a broader range of employers (78.6%). Similarly, a substantial percentage of respondents believed that these programs meet the demands of accrediting or licensing bodies (78.5%), contribute to graduates' career growth (78.6%), and satisfy employers in terms of competence (78.6%), as shown in Figure 2.

These high agreement rates underscore the recognized

value and efficacy of integrated maritime education programs in addressing the multifaceted needs of maritime industry stakeholders. The consensus suggests a widespread acknowledgment of the importance of blending academic knowledge with practical vocational skills to produce well-rounded and competent maritime professionals capable of meeting industry standards and expectations.

Figure 2. Advantages and Motivations in Integrating Academic and Vocational Approaches.

In response to the interview question regarding the benefits and motivations of implementing maritime programs that blend academic and vocational approaches to meet STCW and educational requirements, all interviewees emphasized the significance of integrating these two methods in maritime education.

They highlighted that such an approach cultivates well-rounded graduates capable of thriving in the maritime industry. Recognizing maritime education as a multidisciplinary field, they stressed the importance of combining academic qualifications with practical vocational training to prepare students for the industry effectively.

Furthermore, they emphasized the necessity of imparting crucial skills such as critical thinking and decision-making alongside meeting STCW requirements. They advocated for a teaching approach that merges engineering-level instruction with STCW standards. Success stories shared included notable improvements in graduates' employability and job performance.

B. Challenges in Integrating Academic and Vocational Approaches

The responses to the level of challenge for delivering maritime programs that combine academic courses and vocational training provide valuable insights into the perceived difficulties and obstacles faced by stakeholders in this field, as shown in Figure 3. One notable challenge highlighted by the respondents is the difficulty in finding qualified instructors, with half of the participants (50.0%) indicating it as a significant challenge. This underscores the critical need for qualified faculty members to deliver high-quality education in this domain. Similarly, retaining experienced faculty members also emerges as a significant challenge, with a considerable proportion of respondents (42.9%) acknowledging it. Another critical area of concern

is financial challenges in maintaining the program, with a significant majority (42.9%) indicating it as a considerable challenge.

This suggests that financial resources are a significant constraint in ensuring the sustainability and effectiveness of maritime education programs. Engaging industry stakeholders in the educational process is also recognized as a challenge, albeit to a lesser extent, with 28.6% of respondents acknowledging it as a significant challenge. This underscores the importance of fostering strong partnerships between academia and industry to ensure the relevance and applicability of educational programs to real-world industry needs.

Interestingly, aligning academic and STCW requirements is perceived as a moderate challenge, with 42.9% of respondents indicating it. This suggests that stakeholders recognize the importance of meeting regulatory standards but also acknowledge the complexities involved in aligning them with academic curricula.

Figure 3. The challenge in delivering maritime programs that combine academic courses and vocational training with meeting STCW and accrediting or licensing bodies.

Respondents identified several challenges in response to questions regarding challenges faced when delivering maritime programs that combine academic and vocational approaches. These challenges include finding companies willing to support students' training, needing help to secure financial support from various authorities, and ensuring students are eager to endure extended periods onboard ships. They provided an example of the ongoing challenge of securing student placements on board ships. They highlighted other challenges, such as striking the right balance between theoretical and practical training, resource constraints for maintaining advanced simulation facilities, and the necessity for faculty development to meet diverse educational needs.

They proposed strategies to address these challenges, including fostering collaborative partnerships with industry for resource sharing and implementing flexible teaching methodologies. Another significant challenge highlighted by respondents is the need for faculty members who possess experience as senior officers at sea. They emphasized the

importance of having teachers with expertise in ship maneuvering and cargo handling to teach maritime subjects effectively.

While acknowledging the significance of academic qualifications, they suggested that not all teachers need to hold PhDs. Instead, they recommended balancing technical skills and educational qualifications among the teaching staff to cater to the diverse needs of maritime education.

Another challenge identified is the ability for students to complete their training within the designated study plan. One interviewee proposed a solution involving discussions and agreements with authorities to diversify training opportunities. This would entail moving away from the traditional focus solely on sailing onboard oceangoing vessels. Instead, students could fulfill many training requirements in dry docks, ports, or workshops. This approach offers maritime students flexibility and a broader range of practical experiences.

When asked to indicate the degree to which they perceive the challenges affecting the quality of graduates in Nautical Science and Marine Engineering programs, respondents stated the challenges related to graduates' job prospects, adapting to industry demands, readiness for the workforce, finding employment, industry dissatisfaction with graduates, and practical skill development are perceived as impactful or very impactful by a significant portion of respondents. However, it's important to note that there are also areas where respondents perceive challenges to be less impactful. For instance, challenges affecting the overall quality of education and graduates excelling in either academic or vocational skills but not both are perceived to have a relatively lower impact, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The challenges that may affect the quality of graduates.

Respondents noted several positive changes in response to an interview question regarding the impact of incorporating academic requirements into maritime programs on graduates' quality. They observed that integrating academic components has enhanced graduates' problem-solving abilities and adaptability, ultimately leading to increased efficiency and safety in maritime operations. Additionally, respondents highlighted improvements in graduates' sailing skills and experience, which have enhanced their employability prospects.

However, respondents also identified challenges in

finding quality academicians with sea service experience to teach maritime subjects. They emphasized the importance of teachers possessing both ship experience and academic qualifications to impart knowledge effectively. Furthermore, respondents stressed the necessity of continuous educational improvement to ensure maritime education keeps pace with the evolving industry standards and practices.

C. Industry Stakeholder Involvement

Responding to the question "How involved are industry stakeholders in the maritime education system?" respondents indicated that industry stakeholders are moderately involved, with 71.4% of participants expressing such involvement.

This level of engagement signifies a significant degree of collaboration between academia and industry, which is crucial for ensuring the efficacy and applicability of educational programs in meeting industry requirements. However, it's worth noting that a small proportion of respondents (14.3%) perceive industry stakeholders to be highly involved, suggesting potential opportunities for further partnership and interaction between academia and industry. It should be noted that the presence of respondents who remain neutral or select "other" underscores the diversity of viewpoints regarding the extent of industry involvement in maritime education.

The responses regarding the importance of various roles that industry stakeholders should play in shaping maritime education and training provide valuable insights into stakeholders' perceptions and priorities in this domain, as shown in Figure 5. Facilitating internships, on-the-job training, and industry placements for students are perceived as highly important, with 64.3% of respondents rating it as highly important and 28.6% as necessary. This highlights the importance of practical training and industry exposure in preparing students for real-world challenges.

Offering scholarships, grants, or financial support for students pursuing maritime education is perceived as highly important, with 64.3% of respondents rating it as highly important. This underscores the importance of industry support in making maritime education accessible and affordable for aspiring students.

Participating in advisory boards to guide educational institutions is perceived as highly important, with 57.1% of respondents rating it as highly important and 28.6% as necessary. This emphasizes the importance of industry input in shaping educational strategies and priorities. Offering insights on the latest industry trends and technologies is highly important, with 57.1% of respondents rating it as highly important and 28.6% as necessary. This underscores the role of industry stakeholders in keeping educational programs aligned with current industry practices.

Advocating for policies and regulations that benefit industry and education is considered necessary, with 50.0% of respondents rating it as essential and 42.9% as highly important. This underscores the role of industry stakeholders in shaping the regulatory environment to support the growth and development of maritime education. Regularly reviewing and updating the curriculum to align with industry needs emerges as a critical role, with 50.0% of respondents rating it as essential and 28.6% as highly important.

This underscores the significance of maintaining

curriculum relevance to ensure graduates are equipped with the latest skills and knowledge demanded by the industry. Encouraging research relevant to the maritime industry is also deemed necessary, with 50.0% of respondents rating it as essential and 28.6% as highly important. This highlights the value of industry-driven research in addressing industry challenges and fostering innovation.

Ensuring alignment with international maritime regulations, participating in industry fairs, career guidance, and outreach programs, collaborating on research projects, and creating appropriate assessment methods are perceived as less critical than the critical roles mentioned above. However, they still significantly contribute to the effectiveness and relevance of maritime education and training.

Figure 5. The importance of various roles that industry stakeholders.

In response to the question about the role of industry stakeholders in maritime education and training, interviewees emphasized their vital contribution to shaping future seafarers. They stressed the importance of stakeholders understanding their role in motivating and supporting students throughout their training. Interviewees also highlighted the need for students to demonstrate increased responsibility and commitment during their education.

Interviewees recommended that industry stakeholders actively engage in curriculum design, offer internships, and provide feedback on program effectiveness. They emphasized the value of collaborative initiatives such as joint research projects and resource sharing to bridge the gap between education and industry. Interviewees also suggested establishing advisory boards, fostering continuous dialogue platforms, and implementing mentorship programs to ensure alignment between industry needs and maritime education.

Drawing from her experiences, an interviewee cited the example of vocational schools in Turkey, where limitations

exist on program duration and the issuance of ocean-going licenses. She suggested that maritime faculties should be included in the engineering program to provide a comprehensive education aligned with industry needs.

In response to the open-ended question regarding recommendations for policymakers and education providers to enhance maritime education and training in Oman, interviewees offered several suggestions. Responses are given below:

“Make training mandatory for shipping companies and ensure that students are adequately prepared before training begins. Emphasize the importance of colleges prioritizing student training across various sectors within the maritime industry.”

“Strengthen industry partnerships, allocating funds for advanced simulation technologies, and fostering a regulatory environment conducive to curriculum innovation.”

“Continuous professional development for faculty members and advocated for establishing a national maritime training framework.”

“Emphasize the need for collaboration with project-based industries and stakeholders from universities or industries globally.”

They cautioned against merely meeting minimum STCW requirements and instead urged a focus on forward-thinking elements such as renewable energy, digitalization, decarbonization, and sustainability in maritime education.

In response to the interview question about the future of maritime education, considering the industry's evolving needs and international regulations, interviewees foresee the integration of digitalization, virtual reality training, and curricula emphasizing decarbonization and sustainability. They believe these developments will play a significant role in shaping the future of maritime education. Furthermore, they stress the importance of collaboration with international bodies to ensure alignment with global standards, enabling graduates to compete globally.

D. Opportunities for Improvement

When participants were asked to evaluate the importance of each potential improvement opportunity for maritime education and training, they highlighted several key areas. Industry engagement in curriculum development emerged as crucial, with 42.9% of respondents emphasizing its significance.

Additionally, 42.9% of respondents noted that providing scholarships and financial assistance was vital, underlining the importance of financial support in promoting access to maritime education and attracting talented individuals to the field. Respondents also underscored the value of practical training experiences by indicating that facilitating increased internships and on-the-job training opportunities is highly important (35.7%) and essential (42.9%).

Furthermore, 42.9% of respondents saw enhancing faculty expertise as highly important, emphasizing the role of knowledgeable faculty in delivering high-quality maritime education. Implementing rigorous quality assurance and accreditation processes was also perceived as highly important, with 57.1% of respondents rating it as necessary. Other improvement opportunities, such as broadening academic offerings and collaborating on research projects with industry partners, were considered less critical compared

to the significant opportunities mentioned above.

Respondents suggested recommendations for policymakers and education providers better to align education with industry needs and international requirements. Industry engagement in curriculum development is crucial, with 42.9% of respondents emphasizing its significance, while providing scholarships and financial assistance is vital to promoting access to maritime education, as 42.9% noted. Facilitating internships and enhancing faculty expertise are deemed highly important, underscoring the value of practical training and quality assurance processes in advancing maritime education. In addition, respondents indicated that providing scholarships and financial assistance to aspiring maritime students is perceived as essential (42.9%) and (28.6%) respectively.

This underscores the importance of financial support in promoting access to maritime education and attracting talented individuals to the field. Respondents also indicated that facilitating increased internships and on-the-job training opportunities is highly important (35.7%) and essential (42.9%). This highlights the value of practical training experiences in preparing students for maritime industry demands. Finally, equipping faculty with specialized maritime training is also highly important, with 42.9% of respondents rating it as highly important. Implementing rigorous quality assurance and accreditation processes is also highly important, with 57.1% of respondents rating it as necessary.

The remaining improvement opportunities, such as broadening academic offerings, collaborating on research projects with industry partners, advocating for favorable policies, fostering research in maritime-related fields, delivering career guidance services, allocating resources, and engaging in partnerships with international institutions, are perceived as less critical compared to the significant opportunities mentioned above.

E. Recommendations for policymakers and education providers

Respondents suggested recommendations for policymakers and education providers better to align education with industry needs and international requirements. Below are their responses:

"Reassess the current curriculum to align it with international standards. Ensure direct integration of international requirements into the curriculum and allow for additional exit and entry points for seafarers."

"Reduce elective courses and remove projects. Align all maritime subjects with the IMO/STCW recommended course model, replacing credit-hour-based systems. Ensure all mandatory STCW safety courses are included and incorporate specific disciplinary training."

"Policymakers can enhance education-industry alignment by fostering collaboration, offering incentives for engagement, and supporting internship programs. Simultaneously, education providers should regularly review and update curricula, integrate soft skills development, and promote global collaborations. These measures collectively create a responsive and globally competitive education system that prepares students for the workforce."

"To better align maritime education with industry requirements, it's important to strengthen cadetship programs, ensuring they offer comprehensive training with dedicated instructors onboard. This approach and fostering industry-academia partnerships will facilitate practical, hands-on learning experiences. In addition, adapting curricula to current industry practices and global standards, investing in faculty development, and integrating feedback from industry experts is crucial. A forward-thinking recommendation is to dedicate specific ships for cadet training, providing an immersive, focused training environment that closely mirrors real-world maritime operations."

"Obtain support from industry to update maritime education with technology, such as VR/AR and full mission simulators."

"Introduce a new education program for autonomous ships."

"Close relations with stakeholders, continuous evaluation of new skill requirements, and the development of adaptive and flexible learning methodologies are essential."

"Besides the necessary equipment for maritime education, the government should provide a modern training ship. Furthermore, attention should be given to students for adapting to the latest technological developments."

"Maritime professionals often do not meet MOHERI's mandatory requirement of holding a PhD or master's degree for faculty positions. It is crucial to recognize that maritime specialists have unique paths for professional growth, often achieving the highest qualifications, such as Master Mariner and Chief Engineer with bachelor's degrees. Therefore, the Ministry should consider accepting these professionals to undertake maritime subjects, acknowledging their extensive practical experience and expertise."

"Keep in mind that one year of onboard training combined with the mandatory syllabus from STCW may not always suffice to achieve the goals of collaboration with the maritime industry fully. Therefore, the industry needs to be integrated into the college environment, with industry representatives serving as advisors within the institution."

"Add more restrictions on the academic institutions for the hiring process in the maritime field to have more academic criteria."

"I believe that training cadets onboard is a major component of maritime education, as it embodies the principle of learning by doing."

"In the context of maritime education and training, it is crucial to adapt to the evolving maritime industry continuously. This involves updating curricula to integrate emerging technologies and environmental practices and ensuring that training programs are practically oriented and globally standardized. It is also important to emphasize developing soft skills and adaptability in students, preparing them for a dynamic work environment. Strengthening collaboration with industry stakeholders is essential for ensuring real-world relevance and promoting international exchange programs could benefit broader exposure."

"The students should be educated for deck and engine roles and administrative positions onshore."

These responses offer diverse perspectives, highlighting the contrast between those with experience in sea-related roles and those from academic backgrounds. Some responses advocating for reassessing the curriculum, aligning with

international standards, and integrating industry requirements into the curriculum reflect a practical understanding of the industry's needs. On the other hand, suggestions emphasizing collaboration, soft skills development, and global partnerships are more aligned with an academic approach. These recommendations focus on broader educational strategies and aligning with pedagogical principles rather than specific industry demands.

Recommendations such as strengthening cadetship programs and dedicating specific ships for training underscore the importance of practical, hands-on experiences. These suggestions prioritize real-world training and exposure to industry practices. However, proposals for introducing new education programs for autonomous ships, updating with technological advancements like VR/AR, and emphasizing administrative positions onshore indicate a forward-looking approach, focusing on adapting to future industry trends and expanding career opportunities beyond traditional maritime roles.

Suggestions advocating for closer relations with stakeholders, continuous evaluation of skill requirements, and industry integration within colleges emphasize the importance of aligning education with industry needs. These recommendations prioritize practical relevance and collaboration between academia and industry.

On the other hand, proposals for imposing more academic criteria in hiring processes and ensuring academic qualifications for faculty positions reflect a more traditional academic perspective, emphasizing academic rigor and credentials in maritime education.

The contrast between these responses highlights the complexity of aligning maritime education with industry needs. It underlines the importance of integrating diverse perspectives to ensure comprehensive and practical education and training in the maritime sector.

V. CONCLUSION

This study investigates the advantages and challenges of delivering programs that meet the standards of the STCW convention while incorporating academic courses leading to academic degrees in nautical science and marine engineering. The findings reveal that integrating academic components prepares graduates for industry demands, provides diverse career opportunities, and meets accreditation standards.

However, challenges such as finding qualified instructors with sea service experience and aligning education with evolving industry standards, financial constraints, and industry stakeholder engagement remain significant. Balancing theoretical and practical training, resource constraints and faculty development were challenges. Respondents noted positive changes in graduates' problem-solving abilities, adaptability, and employability due to incorporating academic requirements into maritime programs.

This study underscores the vital role of integrated maritime education programs in meeting industry needs and preparing competent professionals. The study emphasizes the importance of collaboration between academia and industry in shaping educational strategies and priorities to meet evolving industry demands.

For future research studies, it is recommended that

students' and employers' perspectives be further examined to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of maritime education programs. Comparative analyses across different maritime education systems and geographical regions could also clarify the diversity of approaches and outcomes.

It is worth noting that the study's scope was limited to a specific cohort of faculty members and professionals from maritime colleges in Oman, potentially limiting the generalizability of findings. The study did not explore the perspectives of students or employers, which could provide additional insights into the efficacy of maritime education programs.

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